

PECULIARITIES OF DEVELOPING WRITING COMPETENCE

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Annotation: In this article was discussed about peculiarities of developing competence.

Key words: peculiarities, writing, English, competence, developing.

Writing is not only one of the four basic language skills in English learning, it is also an important means of exchanges of ideas in social lives. It is usually considered to be a sign of one's language competence and comprehensive quality. But for most learners, English writing is still a big problem.

Developing writing competence according to FLT of Uzbekistan. At the beginning level (2-4 classes) we teach graphics in EL (handwriting), i. e. teaching to write letters (alphabet) which interrelates with teaching reading as graphic-phonemic correspondence. Pupils must acquire print hand letters. At the same time we form elementary writing skills for conducting communicative-cognitive objectives in the written form. The second stage (5-11 classes) at school must provide more intensive development of writing skills in different situations of communication. Topics and capacity of writing messages is broaden; the quality of produced text in the written form is improved At an academic lyceum and vocational college the level of the language proficiency in writing must provide more effective using it as a means of teaching, self-learning and academic study.

Writing is a complex communicative activity. It helps to communicate in the written form with the help of graphical symbols. Writing is a type of speech activity as "a communicative skill to encode, store and send messages with the help of written symbols". The product of this type of speech activity is a text for reading. Writing techniques and activities can be characterized as controlled (for providing the content and form), guided (as free but a form is given) and free. (Controlled writing proposes using the following activities: coping, gap-filling, re-ordering words, substituting, correcting the facts and dictation. Writing involves content, organization, style, syntax, mechanics, grammar and spelling. It was pointed out that "If we limit our feedback to pointing out or correcting errors, our pupils will concentrate on producing error-free writing, neglecting the interest or even the meaning of the content. The equation teaching writing - error elimination is counterproductive". So it is necessary to conduct feedback in fair balance of content feedback and form

feedback. There are different types of writing performance in English which should be assessed. *Imitative*: at this stage, form is the primary concern to assess learner's skills in the fundamental and basic tasks of writing letters, words, punctuation, and very brief sentences. This category also includes the ability to spell correctly and to perceive phoneme-grapheme correspondences in the English spelling system.

Intensive: this refers to producing appropriate vocabulary within a context, collocations and idioms, and correct grammatical features up to the length of a sentence. Responsive: assessment tasks here require learners to perform at a limited discourse level, connecting sentences into a paragraph and creating a logically connected sequence of two or three paragraphs. Form-focused attention is mostly at the discourse level, with a strong emphasis on context and meaning.

Extensive writing implies successful management of all the processes and strategies of writing for all purposes, up to the length of an essay, a term paper, a major research project report, or even a thesis. Students focus on achieving a purpose, organizing and developing ideas logically, using details to support or illustrate ideas, demonstrating syntactic and lexical variety, and in many cases, engaging in the process of multiple drafts to achieve a final product.

The experienced teachers consider that teachers should ignore the language mistakes that do not hinder learning, so teachers may correct only those mistakes which are very basic and those which affect meaning. Helping the students to concentrate on particular aspects of language, we can tell them that a piece of work will be corrected for only one thing, the use of tenses, for instance. By doing this, we ensure that their work will not be covered by red marks, and we encourage them to focus on particular aspects of written language. We can individualize language work by identifying for each student a few kinds of errors and assigning that focus on these. Where a piece of writing contains a number of common errors, we may photocopy the work (erasing the writer's name) and show it to the whole class, asking them to identify problems. In this way the attention of the class can be drawn to common mistakes and photocopied document can form the basis for remedial work.

To sum up, learning to write is a long, complex and creative process in which a series of language skill practice and the related activities are involved and interrelated. On the one hand, practice of every other language skill helps to bring about improvement in writing proficiency, well-targeted and extended reading and speaking helps to bring about proper, fluent and well-organized creation of writing. On the other hand, constant exposure to different sources of thoughts through different designs works to improve the mind of students. With guiding principles in terms of peer feedback rubric and adequate teacher scaffolding, students tend to revise their drafts more successfully, based on the constructive feedback. Therefore, writing practice, like the practice of the other language skills, is a part of language

learning and a part of quality-oriented education. If English teachers have a deep understanding of the interrelation between writing and the contributing factors, place equal stress on language form and content, integrate writing into the whole process of teaching and learning, then all the efforts made by both teachers and students will be much rewarded.

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